

RE: New FOIA request received for Office of the United States Trade Representative

Ricker, Monique T. EOP/USTR <Monique_T_Ricker@ustr.eop.gov>

Thu 9/23/2021 10:21 AM

To: Kathryn Russ <knruss@ucdavis.edu>

Cc: FN-USTR-FOIA <FN-USTR-FOIA@ustr.eop.gov>

Professor Russ,

This email is the final response of the Office of the United States Trade Representative (USTR) to Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) No. FY21-87 submitted on August 30, 2021 requesting correspondence between USTR and EAGL, NAM, NMPP, USDEC, IDFA, Distilled Spirits, Beer Institute, or Consumer Brand Association about the World Health Organization between June 2016 and June 2021. Per my email dated September 1, 2021, you will need to contact the National Archives and Records Administration (NARA) to request USTR emails dated January 20, 2009 through January 19, 2017.

After a search of our files utilizing eDiscovery software, we located 298 pages of responsive records which we are releasing in part. Because of its size, we have uploaded the record to a file share server accessible for 30 days: <https://drive.max.gov/share/a51809dbf7f35807>

We redacted portions of these documents because we reasonably foresee that disclosure would harm an interest protected by FOIA Exemptions 3 or 6. Exemption 3 allows USTR to withhold information that is protected by a nondisclosure provision in a federal statute other than the FOIA. Here, our Exemption 3 redactions are supported by the confidentiality provisions of the Trade Act, 19 U.S.C. § 2155(g). This part of the Trade Act protects from disclosure advice submitted in confidence by the private sector or non-Federal government to officers or employees of the United States in connection with trade policy matters. In this instance we redacted and withheld confidential advice submitted to USTR by Ms. Morris in her capacity as a cleared adviser on the Industry Trade Advisory Committee on Intellectual Property Rights (ITAC 13). We also withheld non-public contact information and personal signatures because we reasonably foresee that disclosure would harm an interest protected by FOIA Exemption 6, which protects personal information the release of which would not shed light on the performance of the agency's statutory duties.

This constitutes a complete response to your request. You may contact me or my colleague Janice Kaye at FOIA@ustr.eop.gov or 202-395-3419 for further assistance and to discuss any aspect of your request. Additionally, you may contact the Office of Government Information Services (OGIS) at the National Archives and Records Administration to inquire about the FOIA mediation services they offer. The contact information for OGIS is as follows: Office of Government Information Services, National Archives and Records Administration, 8601 Adelphi Road-OGIS, College Park, Maryland 20740-6001, e-mail at ogis@nara.gov; telephone at 202-741-5770; toll free at 1-877-684-6448; or facsimile at 202-741-5769.

If you are not satisfied with the response to this request, you may also administratively appeal by writing to: FOIA Office, ATTN: Janice Kaye, Office of the US Trade Representative, Anacostia Naval Annex, Bldg. 410/Door 123, 250 Murray Lane, S.W., Washington, D.C. 20509.

Your appeal must be postmarked or electronically transmitted within 90 days of the date of the response to your request. Both the letter and the envelope should be clearly marked: "Freedom of Information Act Appeal" and should include a reference to the FOIA Case File number listed above. Heightened security in force may delay mail delivery; therefore we suggest that you also email any such appeal to foia@ustr.eop.gov.

In the event you are dissatisfied with the results of any such appeal, judicial review will thereafter be available to you in the United States District Court for the judicial district in which you reside or have your principal place of business, or in the District of Columbia, where we searched for the records you requested.

Thank you,
Monique

Monique T. Ricker
FOIA Program Manager/Attorney

EXECUTIVE OFFICE OF THE PRESIDENT
OFFICE OF THE UNITED STATES TRADE REPRESENTATIVE
WASHINGTON DC 20508

From: Ricker, Monique T. EOP/USTR
Sent: Wednesday, September 1, 2021 9:57 AM
To: knruss@ucdavis.edu
Cc: FN-USTR-FOIA <FN-USTR-FOIA@ustr.eop.gov>
Subject: RE: New FOIA request received for Office of the United States Trade Representative

Professor Russ,

The Office of the US Trade Representative (USTR) received your two Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) requests for correspondence exchanged with Engaging America's Global Leadership, National Association of Manufacturers, National Milk Producers Federation, US Dairy Export Council, International Dairy Foods Association, Distilled Spirits Council, Beer Institute, or GMA Grocery Manufacturer's Association/Association of Food, Beverage, and Consumer Products Companies that mentions the World Health Organization or its abbreviation, WHO, between June 2016 and June 2021. We have aggregated the requests because they seek similar information (15 CFR 2004.6(c)(2)) and have assigned this request tracking number FY21-87. Please cite this number in any future communications with our office regarding your request.

Please note, legal custody of USTR's unclassified Obama emails officially transferred to the National Archives and Records Administration (NARA) on October 4, 2017. Therefore, you must contact NARA to request USTR emails dated January 20, 2009 through January 19, 2017. Please submit your request to specialaccess_foia@nara.gov.

Our office will provide you with a determination on or before September 27, 2021.

Thank you,
Monique

Monique T. Ricker
FOIA Program Manager/Attorney

EXECUTIVE OFFICE OF THE PRESIDENT

From: National.FOIAPortal@usdoj.gov <National.FOIAPortal@usdoj.gov>
Sent: Sunday, August 29, 2021 8:20 PM
To: FN-USTR-FOIA <FN-USTR-FOIA@ustr.eop.gov>
Subject: New FOIA request received for Office of the United States Trade Representative

Hello,

A new FOIA request was submitted to your agency component:

The following list contains the entire submission submitted August 29, 2021 08:20:01pm ET, and is formatted for ease of viewing and printing.

Contact information

First name	Katheryn
Last name	Russ
Mailing Address	One Shields Avenue Economics Department
City	Davis
State/Province	California
Postal Code	95616
Country	United States
Company/Organization	University of California, Davis
Email	knuss@ucdavis.edu

Request

Request ID 252921

Confirmation ID 252396

Request description I request access to any emails and other written correspondence with the lobbying group, Engaging America's Global Leadership (EAGL) or its related organization, the National Association of Manufacturers (NAM), that mention the World Health Organization or its abbreviation, WHO, between June 2016 and June 2021.

Supporting documentation

Fees

Request category ID	educational
Fee waiver	no

Expedited processing

Expedited Processing	no
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The following table contains the entire submission, and is formatted for ease of copy/pasting into a spreadsheet.

request_id	confirmation_id	address_city	address_country	address_line1	address_line2	address_state_province	address_zip_postal_code	company_organization	email
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request_id confirmation_id address_city address_country address_line1 address_line2 address_state_province address_zip_postal_code company_organization email

252921	252396	Davis	United States	One Shields Avenue	Economics Department	California	95616	University of California, Davis	knruss@ucdavis.edu
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